

TEACHING YOUNG LEARNERS THROUGH WARM-UP ACTIVITIES IN CLASSROOM

L. Shuhratova¹

Abstract:

In this article what kind of influence different types of interesting activities have and how to use them in the lesson is discussed. This article aids teachers to make the lesson more interesting and productive. Usage of this method can improve pupils' communication skills and broaden their outlook, in addition, create friendly atmosphere among classmates.

Key words: warm-up exercises, excitement, team-group game, TESL (Teaching English as a second language), productive, vocabulary skills, English atmosphere.

doi: <https://doi.org/10.2024/2c1pqs18>

Education system is a system that is paid more attention around the world since it is the keystone of development of each country. In addition to this, future of the country is associated with the young considered as a main factor in education system. On this process, teachers play a vital role to make them knowledgeable. In order to achieve such kind of success, each teacher should organize the class effectively and productively, as well. Every lesson should be appeal to the students to get high results

The lesson is valuable and great. Unfortunately, nowadays pupils and students have not enough interest to study and lessons at school, college and also university. This is the main problem of the society at the current time. There are three main causes of this issue:

1. Not having enough qualification and;
2. Not getting sufficient education of teachers;
3. Being careless of students.

There are lots of teachers in the world who gain enough education to teach, however they do not know how to use their knowledge in practice. In that case, some warming up exercises and interesting games can help them to have productive lesson. Firstly, what are warming up exercises?

Warming up exercises are any activity that can aid pupils to get preparation for the lesson and also it boosts their spirit which causes to keep going the lesson with good mood. Students often arrive to class feeling tired or preoccupied with social problems. At that time usage of this method is a great way to start a lesson because it provides a trick to refocus pupil's attention and motivates them to study with excitement at times. Additional to this, by the help of warm-ups teachers can get pupils' attention back to the lesson while they are getting bored or tired. This is a chance for them to have a break during the lesson. Another main point of such kind of activities is creating elementary concept about new theme or topic in students' mind.

¹*Shuhratova Lobaroy Elshod qizi, Namangan State Institute of Foreign Languages*

There are some warm-ups which are clarified below. It is time to move and look through them.

1. Chain drill

It is a very useful and effective activity to increase pupils' interest to learn new words by heart. Firstly, a word is given by teacher and a pupil should tell a word started with the last letter of the word. In this activity, it is banned to repeat a word was told by someone. This is common but productive activity, since by participating in this game pupils start to pay attention pronunciation of every word and improve their selves vocabulary skills. Furthermore, it would be more effective if words students should tell in a certain type. That is to say, if the last lesson was about "nouns", words should be relative to "nouns". In this way, they can extend word skills in a certain type.

2. Phone calling.

This is also prevalent activity. The main purpose of using this activity is aiding to understand each other. In this game, pupils stand in a row like a train and some actions like rising or shaking hand, clap, stand up or sit down are given by the trainer to the last participant in a row. That pupil should show this action to another one. All in all, this action should be continued at the beginning of the row. At the end, the first pupil in the row shows what kind of action was given. According to the last performance, how pupils understood one's action is determined.

This is a great way to teach pupils how to explain something clearly and pay attention to others' condition.

3. Find the word

It is a team-group game. It means that pupils should divide into two groups. Different words are given each group. One of members in each group describe it drawing picture of it or giving definition. Then other members should find what it is. At the end of the game, the winner group is determined according to how many words they found.

When this game is played after a unit it will be sufficient for pupils to revise previous lessons.

These are some examples of warm-ups activities. There are so many exercises and games to attract pupils' attention to the lesson and make it enjoyable. Even TESL (teaching English as a second language) teachers also use such kind of methods to create English atmosphere in the class. Games are great idea to encourage group participation.

In conclusion, since young generation is the future of the country, they should be under control when it comes to get knowledge. On the other hand, teachers are demanded to be more creative and well-qualified. As it is not easy to keep pupils' interest to the lesson, in order to bring students' mind to a learning mode or give a chance to adapt to the new lesson, warm-up exercises during the lesson are worthwhile and beneficial.

References:

[1]. Eragamreddy, N. (2013). *Teaching Creative Thinking Skills*. *IJ-ELTS: International Journal of English Language & Translation Studies*, 1 (2), 4-248.

[2]. Peacock, M. (1997). *The effect of authentic materials on the motivation of EFL learners*. *ELT Journal*, 51 (2), 144-156. Retrieved from

[3]. Schmidt, R. W. (1990). *The Role of Consciousness in Second Language Learning*. *Applied Linguistics*, 11 (2), 129-158. Retrieved from <http://nflrc.hawaii.edu/PDFs/SCHMIDT%20The%20role%20of%20consciousness%20in%20second%20language%20learning.pdf>

[4]. Velandia, R. (2008). *The Role of Warming Up Activities in Adolescent Students' Involvement During the English Class*. *Profile Journal*, 10, 9-26. Retrieved from <http://www.redalyc.org/pdf/1692/169214143002.pdf>